

Plant density, dry matter production, N concentration, and N accumulation of *Sesbania rostrata* at different seeding rate IRRI farm, Philippines, 1987 wet season.

Seeding rate (kg/ha)	Dry matter (mg/ha)		Plant density (plants/m ²)	Leaf N (g/kg)	Stem N (g/kg)	Total plant N (kg/ha)
	Leaf	Stem				
20	1.2	2.7	55	46	9	81
30	1.3	3.0	70	46	8	85
40	1.6	4.1	107	47	9	114
50	1.5	3.9	119	46	8	100
LSD (0.05)	0.1	0.3	10	2	1	8

These results suggest that the higher plant densities resulting from seeding rates above 40 kg/ha decrease organic matter production and N accumulation of sesbania plants. A plant density of 100 plants/m² seems to be optimum for maximum N accumulation.

To achieve a plant density of about 100 plants/m², seeding rates may have to be adjusted for soil textures, climates, and field conditions. ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effects of a growth regulator on rice seedling growth

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Growth regulator Triacantanol has been found effective in increasing biomass production in cereals and vegetable crops.

Triacantanol increases plant height and weight within a few days of application and stimulates nutrient assimilation.

Seeds of semidwarf IET4094 and IR42 and tall indica NC492 rice varieties were soaked 1 h before sowing in 3 concentrations of TRIA (n-Triacantanol): 0.01, 0.10, and 1.00 ppm, with three replications. Root length, root volume,

seedling height, seedling dry weight, and leaf number were recorded 25 d after seeding.

In general, seedlings treated with TRIA were superior to those with no treatment (see table). Late-maturing NC492 and IR42 showed better results than medium-maturing IET4094 in all treatments, for all characters. No toxic, abnormal, or atypical morphological changes were observed at the concentrations used. ■

Effect of n-Triacantanol on rice seedling characters.

n-Triacantanol (mg/liter)	Root length (cm/plant)			Root volume (ml/plant)			Seedling height (cm/plant)			Leaf no. per seedling			Seedling dry wt (mg/plant)		
	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492
0.00	21.2	15.3	17.6	0.2	0.1	0.2	27.4	20.2	37.4	4.9	4.1	4.2	114	137	211
0.01	21.8	21.5	19.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	27.7	25.2	38.6	4.9	4.9	4.7	171	219	237
0.10	21.8	18.6	20.4	0.3	0.2	0.5	27.6	24.1	39.5	5.0	4.9	4.4	181	207	253
1.00	21.8	18.6	18.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	27.6	23.9	37.8	5.0	4.9	4.5	186	202	217
CV (%)	7.8			10.1			4.2			2.9			5.8		
LSD (0.05)	2.6			0.1			2.1			0.2			18		

Fertilizer management

Greenhouse evaluation of urea supergranules (USG) containing diammonium phosphate (DAP) for transplanted rice

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Serious losses of fertilizer N and P to runoff are common in transplanted rainfed ricefields of small farmers in South and Southeast Asia. Losses occur primarily because farmers are unable to properly incorporate fertilizers into soils with varying depths of nonflowing or

flowing floodwaters. A ready-made, balanced NP fertilizer and an alternative application method are needed.

Phosphatic fertilizers containing Ca(H₂PO₄)₂·H₂O (such as single or triple superphosphate [TSP]) are not compatible with urea because of an adduct formation that leads to poor physical quality and caking of USG briquettes. DAP, a common fertilizer for transplanted rice in tropical rice-growing countries, is compatible for preparation of USG. Agronomically, deep placement of USG is efficient in transplanted rice.

We conducted a greenhouse experiment to evaluate basal deep-placed USG containing DAP as NP fertilizer in transplanted rice. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Soil was Vernon clay (Typic

Ustochrept, pH 8.0, CEC 33.0 cmol_c/kg), which in earlier experiments had responded to applied N and P. For a blanket basal application, 100 mg K/kg (as KC1) and 25 mg Zn/kg (as ZnSO₄) were incorporated into the soil before transplanting.

Four hills (three 3-wk-old seedlings/hill) of IR36 were transplanted (20- × 20-cm spacing) in 2-wk presubmerged and puddled soil (32 kg air-dried basis) in a wooden box (40- × 40- × 30-cm inside dimensions) with plastic lining. USG containing DAP (as tablets) was prepared by compacting a mixture of prilled urea (PU) and DAP in a 1:2 proportion. The amounts of N and P used (19.3 mg N/kg and 10.3 mg P/kg, equivalent to 40 kg N and 21 kg P/ha on area basis) were on the steep portion of their response curves for the soil used.

Effect of deep-placed USG containing DAP on grain yield and N and P uptake by transplanted IR36. Greenhouse experiment, IFDC, USA, 1988.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield ^b (g/4 hills per box)	Uptake by grains ^b (g/4 hills per box)	
		N	P
Check	97 c	1.30 e	0.16 d
USG deep placed at transplanting	130 b	1.78 cd	0.18 d
TSP incorporated before transplanting	128 b	1.61 d	0.31 ab
PU+DAP incorporated before transplanting	150 a	1.93 abc	0.32 a
DAP incorporated before transplanting + PU topdressed at panicle initiation	152 a	2.04 ab	0.31 ab
DAP incorporated before transplanting + remaining N as USG deep placed at transplanting	150 a	1.89 bc	0.34 a
TSP incorporated before transplanting + USG deep placed at transplanting	157 a	2.13 a	0.26 bc
USG containing DAP deep placed at transplanting	152 a	2.06 ab	0.26 c
PAPR incorporated before transplanting + USG deep placed at transplanting	147 a	2.07 ab	0.24 c

^aRates of application: 19.3 mg N and 10.3 mg P/kg soil; 619 mg N and 329 mg P/4 hills per box. Estimated rate (on area basis), 40 kg N and 21 kg P/ha. One USG was placed at 110-cm depth in the center of 4 rice hills with 20*20-cm spacing. Incorporation means broadcast and incorporation up to 5-cm depth before transplanting with practically no floodwater. Fertilizer analysis: PU and USG, 46% N; DAP, 21.2% N and 23.5% P; TSP, 20.9% total P; and PAPR from Central Florida (25% acidulation with H₃PO₄, 15.0% total P. ^bMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Plant growth the first 3-4 wk after transplanting was markedly slower for deep-placed USG containing DAP (see table). However, grain yields and N and P uptake were statistically on a par with those for incorporated DAP, TSP, or partially acidulated phosphate rock (PAPR) and deep-placed USG. The PAPR used was as effective as TSP in P availability.

These data suggest that deep-placed USG containing appropriate amounts of DAP may be a judicious choice as a NP fertilizer for small farmers in transplanted rice areas, especially rainfed, where adequate incorporation of fertilizers is not possible because of uncontrolled floodwater and nonavailability of suitable implements. Research under field conditions is under way in India to verify this. ■

Rate and time of N application for direct seeded irrigated rice

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We evaluated rate and time of N application for irrigated rice on a clay loam soil. Soil had pH 7.3 and 0.42% organic C. Treatments were N at 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha in kuruvai (Jun-Sep) and 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg/ha in thaladi (Oct-Feb) and samba (Sep-Jan) seasons, and the initial half of the N applied at four different times in kuruvai (at 10, 20, 30 d after seeding [DAS] and at active tillering) and at five different times in thaladi and samba (at sowing; 10, 20, 30 DAS; and at active tillering). The remaining 50% of N was applied in two equal doses at active tillering and panicle initiation stages, except in treatments where the initial dose itself was applied at active tillering. In this treatment, N was applied in two splits, half at active tillering and half at panicle initiation.

N was broadcast as urea. Basal fertilizer was incorporated in dry soil during kuruvai and samba when dry seeding was done, and in the puddle

Yield and panicles/m² of direct seeded rice with graded rates and time of N application, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	Kuruvai		Thaladi		Samba			
	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
N rate (kg/ha)								
	Kuruvai	Thaladi	and Samba					
0		0	289	2.5	236	1.6	307	3.2
40		50	327	4.3	308	2.8	374	4.5
80		100	362	5.0	332	3.3	434	5.1
120		150	383	5.2	351	3.5	453	5.3
LSD (0.05)			10	0.2	25	0.15	17	0.15
Time of application (initial 50% N)								
At sowing		-	-	-	328	3.1	421	4.9
10 DAS		356	4.8	343	3.5	434	5.0	
20 DAS		384	5.4	339	3.3	470	5.5	
30 DAS		346	4.7	325	3.1	398	4.7	
At tillering		343	4.4	317	3.0	378	4.6	
(LSD 0.05)		12	0.2	ns	0.19	22	0.19	

during thaladi when wet seeding was done. Water was maintained at 2-3 cm for topdressing.

The experiments were laid out in a factorial randomized block design with three replications. Short-duration TKM9, medium-duration IR20, and long-duration CR1009 were sown in kuruvai, thaladi, and samba, respectively. Dry seeds were broadcast during kuruvai and samba; sprouted seeds were broadcast on puddled soil in thaladi.

In general, yields increased with N application in all three seasons (see table). The responses to N application fitted quadratic functions.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Kuruvai } Y &= 2.6 + 0.05 N - 0.0003 N^2 \\ \text{Thaladi } Y &= 1.6 + 0.03 N - 0.0001 N^2 \\ \text{Samba } Y &= 3.1 + 0.03 N - 0.0001 N^2 \end{aligned}$$

The initial 50% N could be applied 20 DAS in kuruvai and samba when dry seeding was done, and 10 DAS in thaladi when sprouted seeds were sown in puddled soil. ■